

Predation by sword-tailed cricket *Anaxipha longipennis* (Serville) (Gryllidae) on eggs of three lepidopterous pests of rice

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We studied the predatory ability of *Anaxipha longipennis* (S.) on eggs of leaffolder (LF) *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis*, green hairy caterpillar *Rivula atimeta*, and green horned caterpillar *Melanitis leda ismene* in the laboratory. Adults of the insect pests collected in the field were caged individually with 35 d-old TN1 rice plants for 24 hours oviposition, in 5 replications. Number of eggs was adjusted to test 10, 20, or 40 per plant. *A. longipennis* starved for 24 hours were reintroduced individually into the cages. The number of eggs consumed was recorded daily for 3 days.

A. longipennis preferred eggs of LF and green hairy caterpillar (see table). By the second day, the crickets had consumed almost all the eggs of the LF and green hairy caterpillar but ate only about one-fourth of the greenhorned caterpillar eggs by the third day. In general, predation on LF and hairy caterpillar eggs was about three times higher than predation on green horned caterpillar eggs. (The eggs of greenhorned caterpillar are larger than those of the other species tested). These results show that *A. longipennis* is capable of making a significant impact on eggs of two species of rice pests.

Cumulative number of eggs of leaffolder, green hairy caterpillar, and green horned caterpillar consumed by the cricket <i>Anaxipha longipennis</i>. IRRI insectary, 1988. ^a/				
Insect species	Egg density(no./cage)	Eggs consumed (cumulative no.)		
		24 hours	48 hours	72 hours
Leaffolder	10	8	10	10
	20	15	18	19
	40	34	40	40
Green hairy caterpillar	10	10	10	10
	20	16	19	19
	40	34	39	40
Greenhorned caterpillar	10	2	2	4
	20	4	5	5
	40	6	10	11
^a / Av of 5 replications.				

Canapi, B.L., E.G. Rubia, J.A. Litsinger, B.M. Shepard, and L.M. Rueda. 1988.
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(Gryllidae) on eggs of three lepidopterous pests of rice. *Int. Rice Res. Newsl.* 13(4): 40-41.